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Impact of Single Parenting on Academic Performance among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone

Zubairu, Zainab Ph.D.

Email: zubairu022@gmail.com

Tel: 08037872125

Department of Educational Foundations, Kaduna State University, Kaduna

Abstract

This study investigated impact of single parenting on academic performance among secondary school students in Zaria Educational zone of Kaduna State. The study intended to appraise how academic performance of secondary school students in Government as a school subject is influenced by single parenting viz-a-viz income status, educational attainment and occupational status. Three research questions and two null-hypotheses each were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The research design used was survey and quasi experimental. Questionnaire and achievement test were the duo instruments used for data collection. The study population is comprised of teachers and students of public secondary schools in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of twelve (12) teachers and Three Hundred and Twenty- Three (323) students were randomly selected from the study population. Achievement test was administered on the students, the questionnaire was filled and returned to the researcher by the teachers. Findings from this study showed that educational attainment of single parents has significant impact on students' academic performance in Government. The study equally identified that occupational status of single parents has a great impact on the academic performance of students in the subject". Based on the findings of this study, it became obvious that the nature of single parental homes determines their wards academic performance in school. Academically, there are various variables that predict one's performance in school subject. These could be those from the family and others from the teachers. The study therefore recommended that stigmatization of single parents and their children should be discouraged forthwith by enacting relevant laws, parents should also be mindful of their children's education as something very important at least before contemplating on divorce and/ or separation from their homes. On a final note, the government should institute a special scholarship to assist students of poor single parents who are presently enrolled in school to caution the effect of their financial weaknesses.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Impact, Single Parenting, Secondary School Students

Introduction

The focus of this study was to investigate impact of single parenting on academic performance among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. Single parenting has replaced the widely known traditionally intact family. Ortese in Muhle (2020) observed that "parents are the first point of contact of a child or children. In situation where both parents are present, it implies that the child would derive more care and attention under their custody. A single parent however is a parent not living with his/her spouse or partner". The entire obligation of raising the child or children therefore falls solely under the care of a single father or mother as the case maybe. Studies by Falana, Bada and Ayodele (2012) asserted that "single parenting results from divorce, separation of various kinds, having children from wedlock or death of one spouse, and leaving the role in the hands of a single parent". Thus, society continues to grapple with the breaking down of the traditional family forming new structures that adversely affect the development of children and in particular, their academics. Education as a whole is believed to recreates both the individuals and the nation, influences values and attitudes for a worthwhile living. It is no surprise that the National Policy on Education (2014) asserted that education is "an instrument par excellence" and the world at large had keyed into this, by recognizing education as the panacea to development and survival of man itself. In defining single parenting, Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, conceived the term as a mother or father who looks after children on their own, without the other partner. It is a situation in which one of the two individuals involved in the conception of the child is being responsible for the upbringing of the child (Whitting and Child in Tenibiaje and Tenibiaje, 2011). In Nigeria, the existence of single parent was formerly unknown and where they exist they were mostly ignored as exceptional cases. Presently, single parenting is the fastest growing family system both inside and outside the shores of the land (Nwachukwu, as cited in Chukwuemeka, 2018). There are widespread cases of single - parenthood across all regions and tribes

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where human beings lived which has further become a major source of concern to the socio - economic and socio - cultural development.

Another important variable known to have been captured in this paper is academic performance. Academic performance is very important in any educational setting, as it indicates the level of a student's competence in respect of the academic content. Indeed, academic performance does create competition among students and it may thus shift focus to the academic content of a course; however, academic performance is a prerequisite in order to achieve success at every other level of educational pursuit. Academic performance is represented by the actual mark obtained by the participants in an examination. Success is typically defined in terms of performance, and grades represent the most obvious and universally accepted indicator of academic performance in the educational context (Hampden - Thompson and Pong in Jaiyeola and Akinjide, 2016). The academic performance of a student determines whether he or she will be considered successful or not. As a result, academic performance is very important in education. Therefore, it is crucial to know and understand which factors are responsible for determining, predicting or causing variance in academic performance.

The family lays the psychosocial, moral and spiritual foundations upon which the overall development of the child can take off. A mother's role in laying the right foundation cannot be over - emphasized. Likewise, studies on father - child relationship suggest that the presence of a father in the home influences significantly the development of a child (Ushie, Emeka, Ononga and Owolabi, 2012) Thus, parenthood is a responsibility that requires the full cooperation of both parents who must ensure the total development of their children. The inference to be drawn from the above submission is that, structurally, a family is either broken or intact. In Nigeria, parental roles are culturally determined and distributed. Maternal roles include child - rearing, home training and playing of complementary roles, while paternal roles include financial provision (food, clothing, and shelter) for the family and discipline of the children. (Uwaifo, 2012). The inference from this submission is that a child is likely to be morally, mentally and emotionally balanced when the caring responsibilities are carried out by both parents. However, these balances may be jeopardized when the responsibilities are being carried out by a single parent.

The above analysis becomes necessary because life in a single - parent family can be stressful for both the child or children and the parent. Such families as Chang and Min (2002) rightly observed are faced with the challenges of diminished financial resources, assumption of new roles and responsibilities, establishment of new patterns in intra - familial interaction and re - organization of routines and schedules. These conditions may not be conducive for effective parenting. This is because when the single parent is overburdened by responsibilities and by their own emotional reaction to their situation, they often become irritable, impatient and insensitive to their children's needs. (Biblarz and Gottainer, in Jaiyeola and Akinjide, 2016) As a result of the substantial prevalence of single parenthood, researchers such as (Ebenuwa - Okoh; 2010; Farooq, Chaudhry, Shafiq and Berhanu, 2011) have extensively examined the consequences of growing up with a single parent for children's education. The outcome of their researches revealed that single parenthood is negatively associated with children's academic performance, however, recent comparative studies show that the strength of the negative relationship varies significantly across countries. (Mandara and Murray, 2006).

Likewise, emerging facts from other studies of developing societies have found no apparently negative effects of single parenthood (Park, 2008; Osunloye, 2008 in Jaiyeola and Akinjide, 2016), rather they found that in sub -Saharan African countries, children in female - headed households tended to have greater educational opportunities in terms of school enrolments and attainment relative to children in male - headed households. On his part, Fadeyi in Jaiyeola and Akinjide (2016) concurred that both parents have their own roles to play in child's education. The father is to provide every necessary tools for the educational advancement while the mother is expected to supplement the efforts of the father. But in the case where the father is absent and the mother is not privileged enough (in terms of income) to cater for all the necessary and basic needs as well as supervising the academic performance of the child, by checking the academic records of the child or by going through their class and lesson notes or books daily. Also giving of counselling supports when needed, these will affect the educational state or level of the child. So also, if a child is not well nurtured and mentally assisted, it will also affect his/her educational outcome. If it were to be a male child, it's likelihood for the child to be anti - social in nature by joining gangs, also, if it were to be a female child, there is likelihood for her to become wayward.

Contributing, Nwachukwu in Asaah (2021), found children from single parent homes to be more hostile, hyperactive and aggressive in nature. Many of the problems that single parents have, are similar as those of two - parents family, but these problems seem more difficult to bear or manage when the home is being tutored by only one person. For example, all children feel hostile towards their parents as they grow - up and try to be independent. But in a situation, where the anger and rebellion are all directed towards one person, it may seem worse, if there is only one to bear it, and not for the two to share. No doubt, a herculean task which may not be easy for an individual parent alone. In case of divorce, separation or death of a parent, children

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are somewhat at greater risk for symptoms of poor psychological adjustment, behavioural and social problems, low self - esteem and poor performance in school. Coupled with this, it is believed in many quarters that children from broken homes have higher incidence of academics, emotional and behavioural problems than other children from intact homes. Recall that single parenthood has existed as a practice of raising children or building family without a spouse or a partner. With this form of building a family, single parenting is now permissible in our societies which formerly stigmatize such a system because it was not much acceptable. Research studies even suggested that children from poor single parent households do not perform well in school as their counterparts from wealthy single parent households (Majoribanks in Watt, 2019).

For the single mothers, they are stigmatized because of patriarchal system of family run in our society (Falana, Bada and Ayodele, 2012). Culturally, it is not acceptable to live with opposite gendered parents. A parent conjointly leaves remarkable impacts on children's behaviours, personality and health. For instance, a girl cannot share every little matter with her father as she can with her mother or vice versa. Attachment is a basic human need to secure relationship between children and caregiver. A child psychiatrist John Bowlby (1958) gave a theory of attachment which clearly explains how children and their parents relationship emerges and influence the emotional and social development of a child. Bowlby designed four stages of attachment from infancy as pre-attachment, attachment in making, clear cut attachment, and formation of reciprocal relationship. All these stages build up a bond and this bond binds parents and their children emotionally (Conor and Scott, 2007). Bowlby's colleague built up another three stages he called detachment, protest and despair experiences children faced when they are separated from their caregivers/parents (Chapman, Whitefield, Felitti, Dube and Edwards, 2004).

When parents are not able to build stronger relationship in their homes, then there are higher chances that children will face some problems such as psychological disorders, such as decrease intelligence, increase anger and violent behaviour (Conor and Scott, 2007; Chapman, Whitefield, Felitti, Bube and Edwards, 2004). This theory is considered best for this work owing to its nature. In all these, children at the primary schools are nonetheless the most fragile group because they are still in their formative years, meaning that any disruptions could have everlasting effect on them. Many studies in Nigeria actually have focused more on parental involvement in children's school activities, compared with family structure such as single parenthood and its effects on the pupils' academic performance. In terms of their educational pursuit, this is relatively determined by the pattern of family or home one comes from, be it wealthy or poor, educated or otherwise. Parents are primarily responsible for the educational and career development of their children (Salami and Alawode, cited by Asah, 2021).

Parents who failed in their responsibilities to assist and guide their children through every stage of development in life may likely have to contend with the poor academic performance of their children sooner or later. The development of wholesome behaviours, as foundation to success in any child is laid upon the home and at the initial stage in life. Parents therefore have a great role to play in seeing to it that students acquire the appropriate social, psychological, moral and academic development. The benefits of two - parents family far outweigh that of a single parent family, as mothers play the traditional role of child care and home-making while the father's role is that of economic responsibilities and discipline of children. Although, these traditional responsibilities of parents are gradually changing. But in single parent families, double responsibilities are required of time, attention and money of the parent. Hence, less attention is given to the education of the child. The situation has become worst today because of the prevailing cost of receiving education as most single parent may not be financially handicapped to handle it. For the few wealthy single parents who are economically viable, the nature of their job will always affect adequate supervision of children's growth and development which may hamper on their academic performance. By and large, Uwaifo (2008) found that differences in academic performance of children exist in terms of those from single parent and those from two parent families. Arising from this, it therefore became imperative to examine the impact of single parenting on academic performance of secondary school students in the study locality.

In recent times, the controversies surrounding academic performance of secondary school students is worth something of discourse and urgent attention. This is especially in view of the roles of families and its subsequent make - up which have assisted or otherwise. Family, as it is known is the first contact for every child born into this world and her contributions no doubt to its academic prowess or otherwise in life cannot be under - estimated. A family type that is headed by a single parent before now is being stigmatized but fast becoming the societal norm. This type of family in the real sense is undoubtedly going to be overburdened with the absence of the other partner for known reason(s). Of concerned, the academic status of students from such homes will suffer the consequences of poor or inadequate funding and character disposition of parents towards them. The national policy on education (2014) recognized the importance of funding on education have suggested that adequate financial provision from all tiers of government for successful implementation of educational programmes are required. It therefore shows that access to education by the ward(s) of a single parent depends on their financial capability. Not too surprised, that children of single parents in the study locality attend public secondary schools.

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Also, single parenthood plays a vital role in determining or otherwise of a person's academic performance in and out - of - school. This is because the level of education of a single parent will go along way to determine what their ward (s) would eventually become in life. The situation is worsened by the fact that the so - called illiterates and unskilled single parents have absolutely no plan for their ward(s) compared to their counterparts who are not only financially buoyant but determine to provide the best for their children's education. There are other categories of single parents with little or no education and at the lower class of a society but determined to give their wards a higher - level education than they could not have achieved. Evidently, the researcher observed that larger population of children attending public schools from single parental homes does not have access to educational facilities, resulting in their mass failure in public and internal examinations due to poor preparation.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated impact of single parenting on academic performance among secondary school students in Zaria Educational zone of Kaduna State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. Find out the impact of income of single parents on academic performance of students in Biology in senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State.
2. Assess the impact of educational attainment of single parents on academic performance of secondary school students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study

1. What is the impact of income of single parents on students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State?
2. Of what impact was educational attainment of single parents on academic performance of secondary school students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State?

Hypotheses

The following null-hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

1. There is no significant impact between income of single parents and academic performance of students in Biology in senior secondary schools.
2. There is no significant impact between educational attainment of single parents and students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools.

Methodology

In this study, descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of this study was comprised of students and teachers of public senior secondary schools under Zaria Educational zone of Kaduna State. There are well over forty - one (41) public and private secondary schools from the selected zone. Out of this, about twenty - eight (28) are public secondary schools with students and teachers' population put at thirty - six thousand, seven hundred and eleven (36,711) and one thousand, three hundred and sixty - six (1,366) respectively. A sample size of three hundred and thirty - five (335) respondents was selected at random from the target population of this study. The study employed the use of questionnaire and achievement tests as major instruments for data collection. A pilot study was carried out in Government Commercial College, Zaria on thirty (30) SS 2 students and eight (8) teachers in different arms of the selected class. The reliability test scores for the instruments was 0.86 and 0.81 both for the achievement test and questionnaire respectively. Data collection was undertaken within ten (10) weeks. Research assistants were identified, trained and motivated on how to assist in the administration of instruments. The data analysis was carried out on the formulated hypotheses using inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the impact of income of single parents on students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State?

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Table 1: Respondents Opinion on the Impact of Single Parental Income on Students' Academic Performance in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone

S/N	ITEMS n = 335	RESPONSE CATEGORIES						
		SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD	SE
1.	In my school, enrolment of students from single parental homes are high due to the cheap cost of education by parents	-	5	4	3	2.1667	.83485	.24400
2.	In spite of the poor facilities in my school, poor single parents in their large numbers prefer to sent their ward to us	2	7	2	2	2.8667	.9847	.2842
3.	Most wealthy single parents in my school promptly pay their ward school fees and acquire other educational materials	3	2	2	5	2.25000	1.2880	.3718
4.	Children from wealthy single parental homes send their wards to boarding school system to display affluence.	3	3	3	3	2.500	1.1.677	.337
5.	Most students from poor single parental homes do not have access to educational material books.	1	2	5	4	2.0000	.9534	.2752
6.	Children from wealthy single parent homes do not have much financial support compared to their counter parts from poor single parents homes.	4	3	2	3	2.6667	1.2309	.3553
7.	Children from poor parental homes do not have much financial support compared to those from wealthy single parental homes	3	2	2	5	2.4500	1.2880	.3718

Source: Field work (2021)

According to the table above, the highest mean response of 2.8667 is on the item that says that in spite of poor facilities in the selected schools; single parents in their large numbers prefer to send their wards there. This item on the influence of income status of single parent on children academic performance showed that a total of 9 of them agreed with this item while 3 disagreed.

Research Question 2

Of what impact was educational attainment of single parents on academic performance of secondary school students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State?

Table 2: Respondents opinion on the influence of single parental educational attainment on the academic performance of students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone

S/N	ITEMS n = 335	RESPONSE CATEGORIES						
		SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	SE
1.	Most educated wealthy parental homes deny their girls access to formal education	-	2	6	4	1.8333	.71774	.20719
2.	As a teacher and parent, single parent do not sponsor the education of their wards as a result of their poor life situation	1	-	6	5	1.7500	.2500	.86603

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3.	Most of the poor single parental homes are headed by women with little or no education	2	3	3	4	2.2500	1.13818	.32856
4.	Most educated single poor parent enroll their wards in schools their counterparts cannot afford	1	4	4	3	22500	.96531	.27866
5.	Children from poor parental homes are privilege to receiving qualitative education as one of the parents will at least be educative.	5	2	3	2	2.8333	1.19342	.34451
6.	It is evident that poor educational status of most single parents encourages them to offer the best education to their wards	3	3	3	3	2.5000	1.16775	.33710

Source: Field work (2021)

According to the response rate on the influence of parental educational attainment on students' academic performance, children from two parental homes are privileged to receiving qualitative education as one of the two parents would at least be educated. This item attracted the highest mean response of 2.8333 and details showed that item 7 agreed while the item found in 5 disagreed.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho1: There is no significant impact between income of single parents and academic performance of students in Biology in senior secondary schools.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Impact of Income Status of Single Parents on the Academic Performance of Students in Government as a Subject.

Variables	N	X	Sd	Df	Correlation index r	P
Students' Academic performance in Biology	333	10.08	4.05	318	.96**	0.000
Income Status	73	33.35	1.53			

Source: Field work (2021)

The result of the correlation test revealed that significant impact exists between the income status of single parental homes and the academic performance of their students in Government. The reason was that the calculated P value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 alpha level of significance at a correlation index value of 0.96. By implication, the null hypothesis stated above is hereby rejected.

Ho2: There is no significant impact between educational attainment of single parents and students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Impact of Educational Attainment of Single Parents and Academic Performance of Students.

Variables	N	X	Sd	df	Correlation index r	P
Students' Academic performance in Biology	333	10.08	4.05	331	.973**	0.000
Educational Attainment	333	33.35	3.79			

Source: Field work (2021)

Correlation is tied to be significant at 0.05 level of significance. The details of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics revealed the existence of significant impact between the educational attainment of single parents and academic performance of students. This was because the PPMC calculated P value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 alpha level at a correlation index t-value of .97. This therefore implies that the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

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Discussions of Findings

The results from tables 1 and 3 of this study revealed that significant impact exists on the income of single parents on academic performance of students in Biology in the study area. It is worthy of note, that income is the conduit pipe to decision making in anything one does. In fact, this had remained the root causes of family conflict and finally separation of homes. Many have attributed the amount of money available to homes to how much they are likely to enjoyed themselves and even provide a sound education to their wards. The aforementioned was in conformity with research studies which suggested that children from poor single parent households do not perform well in school as their counterparts from wealthy single parent households (Majoribanks in Watt, 2019).

Report from the analysis in tables 2 and 4 showed the significant impact existed between educational attainment of single parents and students' academic performance in Biology. Information is power and thus, the reason why it constitutes an essential factor for consideration of successes in any given tasks not to mention the academic lifestyle of students in schools. The works of Dale and Griffith cited by Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) supported this finding in which they found out that a parent's education contribute maximally to any child's performance in school.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it became obvious that the nature of single parental homes determines their wards academic performance in school. Academically, there are various variables that predict one's performance in school subject. These could be those from the family and others from the teachers. However, since this study is concerned with the home factors. Such variables identified to have one impact or the other on the student's academic performance are parental education, number of children in the home, parental occupation and income among others. The fact established in this study has brought about the conclusion that more negative impact could super cede the positive ones on single parental upbringing on the student's academic performance in government within the study area.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations put forward as a result of the outcome of this study:

1. The government should institute a special scholarship to assist students of poor single parents who are presently enrolled in school to caution the effect of their financial weaknesses. To this end, modalities for accessing the funds should be clearly spelt out by setting up a committee.
2. Stigmatization of single parents and their children should be discouraged forthwith by enacting all relevant laws.
3. Parents should be way mindful of the decision they take with respect to their children's education as something very important at least before contemplating on divorce and/ or separation from their matrimonial homes.

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